

Adaptation and Digitalization: A Case Study of Conventional Taxibike in Malang City

Abstract— *The emergence of online taxibike services such as taxibike and Grab has changed the transportation landscape in Indonesia, especially in urban areas such as Malang City. This development brings new challenges and opportunities for conventional taxibike drivers who are now facing a decline in the number of passengers and demands to adapt to digital platforms. This study aims to examine how conventional taxibike drivers respond to the increasingly rapid digitalization of transportation services. Data were collected through surveys and interviews with local drivers in Malang City. The results of the study show that some drivers are still reluctant or unable to join digital platforms due to limited digital literacy or access to smartphones, while others have begun to adapt through informal digital methods such as using WhatsApp to communicate with customers. This study emphasizes the importance of inclusive digital policies so that traditional drivers are not left behind in the digital transition process.*

Keywords— *digitalization, motorcycle taxibike, conventional taxibike, adaptation*

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasingly developing digital era, various sectors of life are experiencing significant changes, including in the transportation industry. One of the major changes that has occurred is the shift from conventional transportation systems to technology-based services, such as the presence of online taxibike. Research results in 2017 proved that Gojek bike contributed IDR 9.9 trillion to the national economy. The research involving more than 7,500 respondents represented the population of driver partners, MSMEs (micro, small, and medium business partners), and consumers in 9 regions, namely Bandung, Bali, Balikpapan, Jabotabek, D.I. Yogyakarta, Makassar, Medan, Palembang, Surabaya. The respondents were partners and consumers who were active in the last 1 month [1]. The results of this research can conclude that the transportation industry continues to change and develop. Online taxibike offers convenience for drivers and passengers through applications that can be accessed directly from mobile devices, so that the ordering, payment, and navigation processes become more efficient. Students like to use online taxibike services because with the development of technology now they can access (order) this online taxibike service using their cellphones. They can make bookings, deliver goods/food, or other activities [2]. However, amidst this rapid development, several conventional taxibikes that we have interviewed are still reluctant to switch professions to become online taxibike drivers. Some of the problems faced by the conventional taxibike community in Malang City in facing this change include income uncertainty, difficulty adapting to technology, and concerns about regulations or tight competition with application-based services. The conflict is based on, among other things, the assumption or perception and jealousy of conventional taxibikes or city transportation that the presence of online taxibikes is the cause of the lack of customers which has an impact on the decline in the income they receive [3]. Although digital-based transportation services are increasingly dominant, most conventional taxibike drivers still stick with their traditional work system. In addition, social and cultural factors [4] also play an important role in their decision to stay in this profession. Several drivers we interviewed felt more

comfortable with a more flexible work system without having to rely on a commission system or rules set by the online taxibike service provider company. On the other hand, there are also concerns about the initial capital needed to join the online taxibike platform, such as ownership of a vehicle that meets standards and the administration costs that must be incurred.

Based on these problems, this study aims to understand more deeply the factors that cause conventional taxibike drivers in Malang City to stick with the conventional system and are reluctant to switch to online taxibikes. In addition, this study also aims to explore potential solutions that can help them face technological challenges, both in the form of digital skills training, incentives, and other strategies that can support their welfare during the digitalization era of transportation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Tariff Factors in Conventional Taxibike Revenue

Conventional taxibike drivers do not have a uniform fare standard like online taxibike services, so the fare is set according to negotiations between drivers and customers. In the conventional taxibike system, customers often must negotiate prices which can lead to fare uncertainty [4]. This can be both an advantage and a challenge, because higher fares can increase income, but can also reduce the number of customers if the price offered is not competitive.

The income of conventional taxibike drivers is significantly influenced by the fare set based on the distance traveled, where the further the trip, the higher the fare charged. A study discussing the satisfaction of online taxibike consumers shows that the fare, along with service quality, has a significant effect on customer satisfaction, both simultaneously and partially [5]. The results of this study emphasize the importance of setting reasonable rates to maintain a balance between customer satisfaction and driver income, both in online and base services. This fare variation creates a dynamic where drivers must consider the balance between attracting customers and obtaining optimal income.

The irregularity of the fare standard on conventional taxibikes, which is different from online taxibike services that apply uniform rates, brings its own advantages and challenges. The flexibility of fare negotiation allows drivers to adjust prices according to travel conditions and distance traveled. However, rates that are too high have the potential to reduce the number of customers because they are considered less competitive. Differences in perception between drivers and customers regarding fair value can create uncertainty in pricing, which ultimately has a direct impact on the economic balance in the traditional transportation sector.

B. The Existence of Conventional Taxibikes in the Development of Online Transportation

Advances in information technology have brought changes to the transportation industry, especially with the emergence of application-based transportation services. This system makes it easier for customers to order services while increasing the chances of drivers getting passengers. Not only pick-ups, but online services also provide pick-up and delivery services,

and even shopping. This shows that the ability of technology to offer services is very high [6]. Consideration of using online taxibikes has become a natural thing for smartphone users. This is not only a trend but also a habit due to various factors such as security guarantees, financial guarantees, health guarantees and driver vaccines, to various discounts. However, this does not mean that this phenomenon does not cause problems. This problem causes problems especially in dealing with conditions in society that do not yet could adapt to technology, for example people in remote areas or the elderly. This is what still makes conventional taxibikes present at various stations or public terminals. This makes conventional taxibike drivers have a more flexible work pattern compared to application-based taxibike drivers. They are not bound by a commission system or certain targets, so they have the freedom to determine their working hours. However, the decreasing public interest in conventional taxibike services has a direct impact on the decline in drivers' daily income [7]. Conventional drivers are not bound by special contracts or targets that require them to focus on their work. These considerations are what make online taxibikes present today.

C. Customer Satisfaction Factors

One of the customer satisfaction factors that influences decision making is ease of access to services. To access traditional taxibike services, passengers must travel to the base [8]. This shows that customers have to sacrifice more time and energy before they can use the service. Unlike application-based services that allow customers to order taxibikes directly from their location, the base system requires customers to find and approach the driver directly. This impracticality can reduce customer satisfaction levels, which ultimately affects their decision to switch to more accessible services [9]. Previous research has shown that ease of access to services has a significant influence on customer satisfaction in using application-based transportation [10]. Changes in customer preferences towards more practical and digital-based services have led to a decrease in the number of conventional taxibike passengers, which ultimately threatens the sustainability of this profession. In addition, research by Mufida and Wulandari shows that the motivation of conventional taxibike drivers is decreasing amidst the dominance of digitalization, due to the lack of support for technology integration systems that can increase customer trust [11]. In line with that, a study by Harianto revealed that conventional taxibike drivers in Surakarta City face major challenges due to the presence of online taxibikes, so they have started implementing adaptation strategies such as sharing telephone numbers with customers, serving long-distance routes without applications, and offering flexibility in price negotiation to retain customers [12]. Furthermore, research shows that consumers currently tend to choose digital-based transportation services because they are considered safer, transparent in price, and easily accessible through applications, making the manual mechanisms used by conventional taxibikes increasingly less in demand and worsening their competitiveness in the modern era [13]. Ease and effectiveness of service are the main factors influencing customer decisions in choosing a transportation service. With reasons of convenience, effectiveness, and the slogan "fast and precise", people will be reluctant to use traditional

taxibikes that are not online-based. This shows that customers tend to choose services that offer instant access, clear travel estimates, and ease of payment. Application-based services not only provide convenience in ordering, but also increase customer trust with features such as real-time route monitoring and driver rating systems. Therefore, the higher the level of convenience and effectiveness of a service, the more likely customers are to choose it over more conventional alternatives.

D. Digitalization and its Impact on Conventional Taxibike

Digitalization has opened up new opportunities in the world of employment, especially with the emergence of technology-based business models that enable global connectivity. By using digital technology, entrepreneurs create global-based businesses in a network that can directly connect consumers, producers, and providers [14]. This shows that digital technology allows business actors to expand their market reach without geographical limitations. With the existence of e-commerce platforms, application-based services, and digital financial systems, interactions between business actors and customers become more efficient and faster. As a result, digitalization not only drives global economic growth, but also creates new job opportunities in the technology sector, digital marketing, and online customer service [15]. The development of digitalization in the employment sector is increasingly rapid, which is marked by the increasing number of companies adopting digital platform-based models. The increase in digital platform-based companies means that the impact of technology will be able to reach more people than before [16]. This shows that digital transformation not only affects business patterns, but also expands the impact of technology on employment. As more and more companies rely on technology, the demand for workers with digital skills is increasing, both in the fields of data analysis, software development, and digital-based system management [17]. Although digitalization brings challenges in the form of disruption to conventional jobs, it also encourages the workforce to adapt to new skills that are more relevant to future industry needs.

III. METHOD

This study uses a qualitative method with interviews as the main instrument. The informants interviewed were 20 conventional taxibike drivers in Malang City (Arjosari Terminal). The data obtained from this interview is referred to as primary data, which is then analyzed to gain an in-depth understanding of the reasons and factors that cause conventional taxibikes to persist.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Reasons not to switch online

TABLE I. TABULATION OF CONVENTIONAL TAXIBIKE INTERVIEWS ON REASONS FOR NOT SWITCHING TO ONLINE TAXIBIKE

Question	Answer
The main reason that makes you still choose to be a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Old and lacking energy (64%)

conventional taxibike rather than switching to an online taxibike?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Easily tired due to health (20%) Not understanding technology (16%)
In your opinion, what are the advantages of working as a conventional taxibike compared to an online taxibike?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Many friends and relatives at the base (84%) No rush around looking for passengers (16%)
In your opinion, what are the disadvantages of working as a conventional taxibike compared to an online taxibike?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If there are few passengers, there will be a loss (82%) Less sophisticated so the area coverage is smaller (18%)
What makes you feel more comfortable working as a conventional taxibike?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No need to use a cellphone (70%) Not tied to a target (30%)

Based on the results of interviews with conventional taxibikes in two different locations, it appears that the main reasons they choose to remain conventional taxibikes are age and health factors, which make them feel more comfortable with a more relaxed job that does not require much energy. One respondent said that they already felt sufficient with the experience of working as a conventional taxibike for years, while others expressed technological limitations such as difficulties in using technology, such as operating a smartphone or touchscreen cellphone. The main advantage of working as a conventional taxibike, in accordance with previous research where taxibike workers really consider peace and freedom in choosing working hours, which are not tied to an application system or strict rules like online taxibikes [18]. They also feel more relaxed, not rushed, and can choose a more flexible operational area.

B. The impact of online taxibike

TABLE II. TABULATION OF CONVENTIONAL TAXIBIKE INTERVIEWS ON THE IMPACT OF ONLINE TAXIBIKE PRESENCE

Main Theme	Summary of Respondents' Answers	Additional Information
The Influence of Online Taxibike Presence	Revenue decreases, many customers switch to online taxibike, revenue decreases, overlapping work areas	Many say that online taxi bikes often enter the conventional taxi bike area
The Influence of Online Taxibike Fares	Fares are similar, but online taxibike is considered superior because of technology	Application technology influences consumer perception

Regulation / Division of Regions	There are regional regulations, but they are often violated by online taxibikes	Considered ineffective / not enforced properly
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Based on the information listed in Table 2, it can be concluded that the presence of online taxibikes reduces the number of conventional taxibike customers. This is because many consumers switch to online taxibikes because they are considered more practical. And even though there are rules regarding the division of areas, online taxibike drivers are often found entering conventional taxibike areas, which of course greatly affects the income of conventional taxibikes. This finding suggests that these losses should be considered by motorcycle taxi drivers as major losses. In addition, although the rates offered by conventional taxibikes and online taxibikes are not much different, conventional taxibikes feel left behind in terms of utilizing technology. This finding is in accordance with previous research findings, where technology that makes things easier for some people sometimes becomes a problem that makes things difficult for some people [19].

C. Factors not to switch online

TABLE III. TABULATION OF THE SEQUENCE OF FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE DECISION TO STAY WITH A CONVENTIONAL TAXIBIKE

Questions	Order from most to less
If ranked, which are the largest to smallest factors that influence your decision?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Health (14 respondents) Technology (12 respondents) Fortune (13 respondents) Mobilization (8 respondents)

Based on the order of factors influencing respondents' decisions to remain conventional taxibikes, the most influential main factor is health conditions, followed by technological constraints such as the inability to use a touchscreen cellphone. Other factors such as the belief that there is still sustenance even if you are not an online taxibike also influence but are not as strong as health and technology factors. Finally, the lack of flexibility in conventional taxibike services compared to online taxibikes is considered an additional constraint, but not the main factor in decision making. This shows that physical aspects and personal comfort are the biggest considerations in maintaining a profession as a conventional taxibike.

Initially, there was an unwritten agreement regarding the division of work areas between conventional taxibikes and online taxibikes. One form of this agreement is the distance rule, where online taxibikes are not allowed to pick up passengers within a certain radius, for example 100 meters or 1 km from the base location. However, the current conditions have changed a lot. This agreement is often violated by online taxibike drivers. They continue to pick up passengers around the base area, thus creating unhealthy competition. This causes conventional taxibike income to decrease because customers prefer services that are considered more practical. In addition, conventional taxibikes do not have the convenience of moving locations because they stay at a certain

point. Meanwhile, online taxibikes could receive orders from various places with the help of application technology. Coordination between conventional taxibike drivers and online taxibikes existed at the community level or between individuals. However, there was no direct intervention from the online taxibike service provider company in maintaining or enforcing the division of areas. In short, conventional taxibike drivers keep the area exclusive to conventional taxibikes and avoid conflict with online taxibikes. Meanwhile, online taxibike drivers, initially complied with the distance rule, but now often violate it due to economic needs or ignorance. Online taxibike providers do not have an active role in regulating the division of areas or resolving conflicts that occur in the field. Several respondents said that there should be restrictions on passenger pick-up areas so as not to collide with conventional taxibikes. However, because there is no official policy, the implementation of such solutions is difficult to do.

V. CONCLUSION

The digitalization era has revolutionized the transportation system through the presence of online taxibike services. This study concludes that conventional taxibikes in Malang City can survive due to age factors, limited mastery of technology, and the convenience of a more flexible traditional work system that does not require daily targets. Based on these findings, we recommend basic technology training for conventional taxibike drivers who are still productive so that they can adapt if needed, as well as fairer regulations to regulate the division of operational areas between conventional taxibikes and online. This study has limitations in the limited number of respondents and the narrow scope of the area, so for further research it is recommended to involve more locations and quantitative data in order to obtain a more comprehensive picture of the impact of digitalization on traditional transportation.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data used in this study are available upon request to the corresponding author. Because the data involve personal information of participants that is protected by confidentiality, access to the data will be provided on a limited basis for academic and non-commercial purposes, in accordance with ethical approval and data use agreements.

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